

WAYS OF DEVELOPING RHYTHMIC SKILLS IN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Sotiboldiyeva Mahzuna Qaxramon qizi

Uz SWLU

email: mahzunaxonsotiboldiyeva@gmail.com

Annotation: This article devoted to open the basic methods of developing rhythmic skills in language learners. In addition to this, in the article an important component of accentuation was noted.

Key words: *speech activity, pronunciation skills, Phonematicity, distinctive feature, Stylistic principle, phonemic correct pronunciation, phonemic articulation.*

Even being English the most spoken language in the world, its pronunciation is many times considered less important than grammar or written comprehension. But it must be remembered that the four main abilities of a language - reading, writing, listening and speaking - have all the same importance. Just like Latin was the language meant to gather people as the Roman Empire went on its row of conquests all over Europe and later, during the Enlightenment Period, it was French, at this moment English has this function. However, as English has become more and more popular, people of all cultures learn and speak the language around the whole world. We should ask ourselves, then, how much English language is influenced by other languages and how much of this influence is acceptable.

Phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the methods of education of human speech sounds. Material of phonetics is a combination of all audio equipment (phonemes and intonemes). Language as a communication tool has emerged as the audio language. The listener will not understand it if he does not know own pronunciation skills. Having solid pronunciation skills ensures the normal functioning of all types of speech activity. Phonetics is not taught in school

as independent and mastering pronunciation skills, it is carried out in the courses of training speaking and reading. Requirements to pronunciation skills determined on the basis of the principle of approximation that is the correct pronunciation. The followings are basic requirements for pronunciation skills:

1. Phonematicity — suggests the degree of accuracy of phonetic speech processing, it is not hard enough for the understanding of its interlocutor.

2. Fluency — the degree of automation of pronunciation skills, allowing students to speak at the right pace of speech. (110–130 in German language; 110–150 in English language signs per minute.). Students must master the intonation structure for the most common types of sentences. Selection of the material is done according to the following principles:

1. Compliance with the communication requirements (distinctive feature)
2. Stylistic principle (the literary language or dialect)[1].

At the initial stage of training focuses on the automation of pronunciation skills, and at the last stage explains the general laws of pronunciation skills in native and foreign language. Under the speech pronunciation listening skills refers to the skills of phonemic correct pronunciation of all the sounds in the flow of speech, understanding all the sounds with the listening speech. Under the rhythmic intonation skills refers to the skills of intonation and rhythmically correct execution of speech and understanding the speech of others. When we talk about teaching phonetics at school there is considered the formation of phonemic articulation, intonation and rhythmic patterns. The program provides the students mastering the sounds of the English language, tone of the narrative (affirmative and negative), imperative and interrogative sentences (Grade 5), intonation offers a frame structure (Grade 6) and intonation of complex sentences (Grade 7) The sequence of the study of sounds in the practical nature of teaching foreign languages in the secondary school is primarily determined by the two positions:

- 1) the need to develop an oral-language skills at the outset, already in an

introductory course;

2) the need to consider phonetic difficulties. The leading method of mastering the pronunciation is repeated listening and imitative most accurate sound reproduction and subsequent use of it in the speech flow.

Phonetic exercises are the decisive factor in creating pronunciation skills are the followings:

1. Exercises on the perception of a new sound to the ear: a. speech stream — a first speech sample of a teacher speech, then in mechanical recording. b. a separate word, in isolation, in combination with the notes master, if the phoneme of the second group; c. followed by a first repeat reproduction of a single word, then the speech sample.

2. Exercises to reproduce phonetic phenomenon which are used collective and individual forms of work. a. reproduction of individual students and the teacher correcting possible errors. b. choral play together with the teacher. c. choral play unsupervised. d. The individual playback of individual students in order to control the formation of the right auditory-speech motor sample.

3. Training exercises for the automation of pronunciation of speech skills in conditional phonetic speech directed exercises (e. g., rhymes). These types of exercises are conventionally speech exercises with monological and dialogical nature, which study the phonemes trained in the conditional verbal communication in teaching speech[2].

In general, linguists distinguish several main types of English intonation, where falling intonation and rising intonation are the two basic types. The fall-rise pattern has the meaning of both, i. e. both closed and open meaning. This signifies both definiteness and indefiniteness simultaneously, in the sense that a referent is instantiated but the utterance is not yet completed or in the sense that the speaker feels some hesitancy, reservation, doubt or uncertainty. The rise-fall pattern incorporates the fall of completion or assurance of the first pattern with the

emotional overtone of a high pitch in the middle of the utterance. This is a so-called swell tone used for emphatic meaning: as the tone swells, the meaning or emphasis increases. Other main types of intonation include high fall, low fall, fall-rise, high rise, midlevel rise, low rise. They are variations of the two basic types of intonation. Language learners should master the typical patterns of standard falling and rising intonation before studying their variations.

Pitch is an important component of accentuation, or prominence, both at the level of individual words and at the level of longer utterances. Pitch is the degree of height of our voice in speech. Normal speaking pitch is at midlevel. Intonation is formed by certain pitch changes, characteristic of a given language, for example, falling intonation is formed by pitch changes from high to low, and rising intonation is formed by pitch changes from low to high. The pitch of the voice is determined by the frequency with which the vocal cords vibrate., The frequency of vibration of the vocal cords is in turn determined by their thickness their length and their tension. The modal pitch of the voice, i. e. one's natural average pitch level, depends on the size of the vocal cords. In general, men have thicker and longer vocal cords than women and children do. As a result, the modal pitch of a man's voice is generally lower than that of a woman or a child. In addition to its modal pitch, every individual voice has a pitch range which can be achieved by adjustments of the vocal cords. By tightening the vocal cords, a person can raise the pitch of the voice (vocal pitch); by loosening them, one can lower vocal pitch. There is also a natural variation in pitch associated with the amount of air that is expended during speech. When the airflow through the glottis is great, it causes the vocal cords to vibrate quickly.

After all, for understanding the meaning of the entire sentence the audited must keep the beginning of sentences in memory. Psychological difficulties of audition are caused as audited speech (live or referred in the manual recording), situational dialogic or contextual monologue speech, speech of acquaintance or a

stranger (speaker), etc. Experience shows that the quality of listening depends on the nature of speech: speech in direct communication is better understood (*ceteris paribus*), than are in the manual recording. Because understanding the live speech is facilitated by extra-linguistic factors such as the situation, gestures, facial expressions, articulating. Situational dialogic speech in the manual recording is generally understood with great difficulty than the speech of contextual monologue. Situational speech, followed by the visual side, is understood much more easily than contextual. Among the factors complicating listening, are also features of the speaker voice data (voice, height) and rate of speech.

By linguistic difficulties of audited text refers, first of all, the presence in the text of a certain number of unknown and incomprehensible words, language material. With regard to the difficulty of understanding the text due to ignorance of the language, it is important as the nature of language itself, and the location of unknown words in the text. Unfamiliar words in the beginning of the text are difficult to understand or properly orient the listener with respect to the subsequent detention of the audited text. The least negative impact on understanding occurs when the unfamiliar word is in the middle of the text or at the end of it, when its value is easily determined by the context. Grammatical phenomena may also be different in understanding the degree of the difficulties[3]. Grammatical phenomena may also be different in the degree of understanding of the difficulties. “Non-essential” for understanding may be, for example, the end of adjectives; personal endings of verbs, if properly understood personal pronoun or a noun; the order of words in the interrogative sentence, and others. For language difficulties should also include stylistic features of the text (figurative means, dialect, colloquial expressions, names, realities) and phonetic features of the audited speech: strangeness of pronunciation of native speaker, inappropriate or promiscuous of pronunciation and others[4]. The methodical literature in terms of content and composition distinguishes between “favorable”, “neutral”, “difficult”

contexts. Favorably it will be interesting for the class the simple, clear language, and logical in its development of plot or fable context.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that teaching English pronunciation is an area of language teaching that many English teachers avoid. While there are many textbooks and instruction manuals available, as well as books on the theories and methodologies of language teaching there is comparatively little on learning pronunciation. Many students tend to think of pronunciation primarily as accurate production of the sounds of English words, but this is neither the only aspect of the problem nor the only important one. Consequently, one way in which you can help students improve is by ensuring that they are aware of all of the important issues.

REFERENCES:

1. Witt N.V., Emotional factor in learning a foreign language //M.: MGPI 1971, p.124.
2. Lyubimov N.A., Phonetic aspect of communication in a foreign language. — L., 1988.
3. Porojnyak N.F., Development of phonetic skills of students of non-philological high schools // Young scientist. — 2014. — №9. — S. 556–559.
4. Лисенко Д.М. О членении человеком непрерывного потока речи на слова // Механизмы речеобразования и восприятия сложных звуков / Д.М. Лисенко. – М., 1966. – 294 с.